

EGYPT AT THE CROSSROAD OF MODERNITY AND TRADITION: REFLECTIONS FROM CAIRO TRILOGY

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Abstract

*First half of the Twentieth century was not different for Egypt, since, like many other countries of West Asia it was also besieged with problems from all corners. Politically the country was under occupation of British. Economically she was suffering the wrath from rising prices of commodities along with influx of foreign armies and troops and ideologically it was at the crossroad of modernity and Islam. In this backdrop Naguib Mahfouz documents the details of the socio-political realities of the time in his monumental work *al Thulathiyat*; (the three volume Trilogy). The famous *al Thulathiyat* (The Trilogy) by portraying a patriarchal family of Cairo brings in light not only the tradition and modernity but also the subjects like science, religion, ethics and morality being discussed by the various characters of Mahfouz. These selected novels by documenting the socio-political nuances of the period between two World Wars lead to see Egypt in a transition phase or at the cross road of ideas.*

Keywords: Egypt, Modernity, Islam, Tradition, Novel and Cairo Trilogy.

Introduction

The selected novels portray the society of Egypt starting from First World War to the end of the Second World War. The first volume of trilogy *Bain al Qasrain* (Palace Walk) mirrors the Cairene society during the period of the First World War and continues till the 1919 revolution which brought independence for the country. A Cairene patriarchal family is being portrayed, which brings all the socio-political issues into its realm. Through a family saga that is controlled and ruled by a patriarch named al Seyyid Ahmad Abdul Jawwad, with his authoritarian attitude of a traditionalist, Second volume from the trilogy *Qasr al Shaoq* (Palace of Desire) draws a picture of independent Egypt under the constitutional rule. The novel starts from 1924 and ends with the death

of revolutionary leader Sa'ad Zaghlul in 1927, continuing with the patriarchal family saga, the novel focuses more bluntly on the idea of tradition and modernity, religion and science and freedom and democracy. As a main protagonist of the novel, youngest son of Abdul Jawwad remains at the center of focus, who brings all those ideological conflicts and resultant confusions of the society into light.

Moving forward to *Al Sukkariyyah* (the Sugar Street) third volume of the trilogy, it is noticed that the novel brings into light the socio-political developments from the thirties and forties of the last century through the third generation of the patriarch. The author declares the end of the tradition of patriarchy and traditional values while proclaims the victory of modernity over the tradition. As a result of this, responsive ideologies like communism, socialism and Islamic revivalism was discussed through the characters like Abdul Mun'im and Ahmad.

Egypt between Two World Wars

In the period of inter War the socio- economic and political condition of Egypt was besieged with many problems. Politically, though she got its partial independence in 1922 with the establishment of its own liberal constitution in the following year, but she could not make free herself from the heavy grip of foreigners till the next revolution of 1952. This foreign domination on her political life made the country's affair complicated at internal level too. The British as a foreign dominant power who had reserved four points under its direct control including Suez Canal, foreign affairs, Sudan issue and minority rights, used the rival powers of the country for its own benefit (Marsot, 1985: 82-85). As the rivalry between the Wafd, the only victorious nationalist party and the Palace created a threat to the constitutional functioning of the parliament.

During this period the socio economic condition of the society aggravated because of government's negligence of the problem or its involvement with a greater issue that each successive government considered more important than its internal issue or increasing people's grievances. That problem was the settling down the country's political issue with Britain by negotiating a treaty, which could not be possible until 1936. But when the treaty was discussed it left the complication

lying there at the same situation where it was earlier. The Egyptian government and liberal political parties which was opposing the foreign hand into Egyptian internal matter showed its compromising mood by signing on the treaty with Britain which crushed the hope of people into the county. Thus the experiment with the democracy, the constitution, the parliament and even the government proved to be a kind of mockery throughout the period. People became disillusioned and disappointed towards the whole system.

On the other side the society went through intensive process of social restructuring in the period of thirty years after independence in 1922. Between 1917 and 1947, the total population of Egypt increased by nearly 67 per cent; while the available crop area increased only by 20 percent. The resulting pressure on the land caused a great acceleration of the movement from the country to city. It may be understood that the number of inhabitants in Cairo increased from 791,000 in 1917 to 2,0100 in 1947 and in Alexandria from 445,000 to 919,000 in the same period. In the decade 1937-1947, the rural population grew by eleven per cent, while the urban population grew by 44 per cent (Marsot, 1985: 181-185).

The doubling of population in these years particularly in the major cities could not fail to have grave economic, social and political consequences. The influx of cheap labor from the country kept down employment, wages, and living standards among the unskilled masses of working people. This even caused socially and psychologically uprooting of large sections of the population from the controls of the still closely knitted village society, and their inevitable drifting into the appalling crowded city quarters, where the collectivity once existed had completely broken down and the social guidance that it provided had vanished. In this regard Nadav Safaran noted,

that “in the absence of a group life and moral and social restraints, the pursuit of the pleasures and attractions of the city and of the means to acquire them, largely occupied the place of values, and frustration met in their pursuit became the source of dangerous resentment. Idleness, precarious livelihood, rootlessness, crowding, desires in excess of reach, all contributed, in turn, to turning these people into responsive and easily accessible material for the political agitator and social troublemaker, who were not lacking throughout these period” (Marsot, 1985:182).

The new industries created a new class of industrial proletariat having a little or no connection with the traditional society from where they migrated. But in front of the uncertainties of the market and the values of modern society to which they were newly exposed, generated one another problem for the social order of the country. Says Safaran “Fully exposed to the environment and discipline of the modern life, its members lacking the education and experience to evolve or assimilate an intellectual and moral outlook capable of coping with them, Insecure in their livelihood, due to the vagaries of employment and the fluctuations of real value of wages, and unable to protect themselves against large reserve of unemployed they were easily susceptible to the appeals of the demagogue or the religious fundamentalists and ready to resort to violence” (Marsot, 1985: 184).

The tendency of Westernization had the crucial effect of creating a break between generations. On the moral level, this cleavage between generations had the effect of weakening the authority of parents, thereby undermining one of the most important social controls. Thus, among nearly all the major groups comprising the urban population, the general economic and social developments and the pressure of the population had the effect of weakening the main instruments of social control. It created explosive social and political potentialities. Both of these effects were further aggravated by the circumstances of World War 11 and its aftermath.

The above economic, political, social and ideological aspects and cries were sharply discussed among the then intellectuals and literary personalities. They were engrossed in debates of ideas and cultures, morals and ethics, values and politics. These contexts and facts of the Egyptian society impacted and influenced Naguib Mahfouz’s thinking and writings.

The Cairo Trilogy

First Volume: Bain al Qasrain (1956) Palace Walk

The significance of Mahfouz’s writing regarding those upheavals and issues raised above is that his novels depict the true picture of the society. The trilogy focuses on the nuances of socio-political undercurrents of Egypt from the period of Two World Wars and their impact on the society. It shows the ideological confusion among majority

of the young generations in terms of the clash of modernity with a traditional Islamic society. Regarding this Mahfouz himself says in one of his interviews “Kamal from the trilogy represents my own generation—our ideas, our choices, our dilemmas and psychological crises—and so his character is in that sense autobiographical” (El Shabrawy, 1992).

The characters like Abdel Jawwad, Amina the famous patriarch and matriarch symbolizes the traditional way of life. But with the proceeding chapters they tend to end their grip on the generations to come. It shows clearly the triumph of the modernity over the other. This is what has been claimed by Sara “This cleverly-written novel is about the structure of the family unit, the role of the patriarch and matriarch, and the political repercussions that ensue as barriers are broken and roles become reversed over time” (Zakzouk, August, 2021). The political undercurrents of the time have been reflected through the character of Fahmy a nationalist and a law student. Though he falls martyred in one of the protests to support Sa’ad Zaghlul at the time of 1919 revolution but he is also the first from Abdel Jawwad family who rejects his father, the patriarch’s understanding of the things. Furthermore, he shows the temper of patriotism in Egypt’s new generation which brings the country its most cherished goal at the end: the Independence. When Daniel one of the reviewers of Palace walk says “According to Mahfouz, the First World War signaled major changes in the traditional Muslim family structure. When Fahmi, the second son, refuses to comply with Ahmad's order to stop his nationalistic activities, he acts as a modern son (Pipes, February 12, 1990).” He tries to bring idea home that this generation along with their education is different from that earlier one. For example, the *Urabi* movement which was suppressed by British forces almost four decades ago. Now the society is different, this generation is more organized and suited to take on the rivals. Indeed, this is the idea of Mahfouz. The argument between the father and son brings the intensity and zeal of patriotism of the son into light. When his father comes to know about his activities, and tries to convince him not to be indulged into such dangerous acts. First the boy apologetically confesses that I am not alone. There are many who do that and “we are all ready to sacrifice ourselves for our country ((Mahfouz, & Hutchinson, 1956, 1991: 537,422)).” the son further elaborates his argument by rejecting his father’s explanation when his father says. Do you know? “God does not

protect those who expose themselves to danger needlessly.” The answer from the boy was “But God also urges believers to struggle.” At this father says furiously, “that’s struggle for the sake of God” the answer from Fahmy was, “we are struggling for God’s sake too every honorable struggle advances God’s cause ((Mahfouz, & Hutchinson, 1956, 1991: 537,423)).” certainly the heated argument between father and son confirms both the point the nationalism and patriotism in the heart of fahmy and rejection of father’s notion of understanding which is indeed a harbinger of modernity.

When Daniel writes about palace walk he asserts these two important points about Mahfouz and his Writing. His love for city, the second: his love for human’s life. “Mahfouz can be compared to Honoré Balzac in his love for the life of a particular great city, high and low, and his tolerance for the ambiguity in the heart of each human. At its best, *Palace Walk* is full of insight about the human condition” (Pipes, February 12, 1990). Mahfouz writes about Cairo and its people. He plays with the minds of common people and dignifies the Cairo’s historicity. He feels the pain in Amina’s heart and he notes the hypocrisy of Abd al Jawwad. He roams around the city in search of amusement in the character of Yasin like a beast and he burns sitting in café with nationalistic fire in the character of Fahmy. He is indeed unique and master of his work.

“I am a man. I am the one who commands and forbids. I will not accept any criticism of my behavior. All I ask you is to obey me. Don’t force me to discipline you” (Mahfouz, & Hutchinson, 1956,1991: 328-329, 4). When Abdal Jawwad shouts these words to his wife Amina, it clarifies his status in the society which is indeed a traditional one. When he characterizes patriarch he brings the arrogance in him out. At the same time when he writes about city he describes the truth. He does not forget to add the cultural taboo to the city.

“There was nothing to attract the eye except the minarets of the ancient seminaries of *Qal’un* and *Barquq*, which loomed up like ghostly giants enjoying a night out by the light of gleaming stars” (Mahfouz, & Hutchinson, 1956,1991: 327,2). When, he characterizes a boisterous hearts like Yasin who was compelled to sit in the home due to the unwanted situations. His frustrations come out in these words. “Your life is destroyed, your son of Ahmad Abd al Jawwad. How the Australians

gloat at your fate? Woe to me, expelled from Ezbekiya entertainment district, a prisoner in al Gamaliya, it's all the fault of the War" (Mahfouz, & Hutchinson, 1956,1991: 447,242).

Again these three texts taken from the novel show another facet of the society too. If Amina being women succumbs to the pressure of her husband, it shows the traditionalism of the Arabian society. The next one brings both the historicity and cultural character of the city into light, while the third one is about the compulsion created by the presence of Australian forces in the First World War era and frustration of masses.

Second volume: Qasr al Shawq (1956) Place of Desire

Moving to the other novel *Qasr al Showq or Palace of Desire*, the novel takes the scene of earlier volume further ahead. Here we can see the society at the crossroad of ideas. The main protagonist of the novel Kamal symbolizes the youth of the society. He was shown here a confident and mature young Egyptian who takes his decisions regarding his life and his future goal. The novel begins in 1924 with the beginning of the liberal constitution in the country and ends in 1927 with the death of Saad Zaghlul the country's most revered leader. The author brings two families into play along with the Abdel Jawwad Family. The story revolves around tradition and modernity depicted through all the families in their specific space. The famous Abd al Jawwad family which was ruled with an iron fist in the previous book now seems to be losing its grip on the house hold. As, none of their children seem to be preserving their ideas and traditions. At the other hand, one new entrant the Shaddad family, the family of Kamal's friend and his beloved, which was symbolized as a modern family where everyone finds his/her choices and desires to be met easily. This family is characterized as the symbol of development and progress. Another one Shawkat family where both Ablel Jawwad's daughters were married symbolizes the same. Both these families against Abdul Jawwad symbolize the modern families, adopting the ideas of freedom and equality. The women are free to pursue their educations, even they are independent to adopt their way of life. It fully captures the mood of transition prevalent in the society. Here says Richard in one of the reviews of novel.

The second novel, like the first, is leisurely in its progress; it embraces a wide range of tones and stylistic strategies deriving from Mahfouz's systematic study of the major novels of England, Russia and,

especially, France. It is richly descriptive of rooms and streets; it is full of incident and suggestive in psychology. (...) There's a sense in which *Palace of Desire* is a transitional novel" Dyer, (1991).

What are the senses which suggest that it is in transitional mode? Of course, the characters and their movements are the best tool to see the transition taking place in the society. The best example of this change is Shawkat family. The family certainly was more lenient than Al Jawwad family. Not only have the ladies of the house had freedom to visit neighbor's houses at ease but also they could smoke and sing if they wish so. Particularly Aisha the younger daughter of Abd al Jawwad who was married to Mr Khalil Shawkat, having a nice voice used to sing and her husband loved to play music. The male members of the family were comfortable to drink even in their house. They do not have to hide it from any one because they all were agreed upon a point that whatever one wishes to, they could do. Here nothing is considered bad until it harms the other. These points are made by Khadija when she disapprovingly complains about her sister to her mother. And she shows her concern saying that, see; mother: how her husband spoils her.

She says

Her husband made pampers her so dreadfully he spoils her. He has made her his partner in all his depraved acts. Smoking is not only his bad habit. He drinks liquor at home without any embarrassment. There is always a bottle in his house, as though it were one of the necessities of life. He will get her hooked on drink just as he did with tobacco" (Mahfouz, & Hutchinson, 1956,1991: 712,242).

This idea of change is being supported by Issa through these words "Whereas the first volume, portraying the old established order, moves slowly, the second proceeds at a faster pace, reflecting the change taking place in Cairene life during the years covered" (peter, 1991).

When it comes to pace of the novel having society's pace in mind Mahfouz's description regarding this, seems more relevant. Mahfouz draws a picture of those liberals, west oriented people and particularly the youths who aspired to be free from religion and live a free life. Free from every shackles of religion as Husayn sheds light replying a question asked by kamal who hesitates to eat ham and drink beer. Husayn asks

Despite all this, your celebrations in the month of Ramadan are beyond description. Lights are lit, the Quran is recited in the reception hall, the call of prayer rings out in the gentle men's parlor isn't that so?" my father celebrates the nights of Ramadan out of love, respect and veneration for the traditions my grandfather observed. He and mama are also scrupulous about fasting ((Mahfouz, & Hutchinson, 1956,1991: 689,193)).

Through this, one can easily make a point that the author through one of his young character declares that the fasting and other religious duties are the things of past. There was a point when my grandparents used to do all these. Now my parents do it out of respect for my grandparents. The point is asserted by David by saying that when it comes to ideas and ideology of the World. The novels seem a perfect example which brings the ongoing war of ideas into light. Where he says

The second installment situates the rogue-patriarch against the background of deteriorating traditions, filial insubordination, and the rising tide of nationalism and resentment of British domination. (...) When the novel examines states of consciousness, metaphysics, and the history of ideas, it is sententious. Mahfouz is better on collisions than on musings. It's the wit, irony, and rich sense of incongruity in life that make *Palace of Desire* an important novel of civilization" (Castronovo, 1991).

What is the ideological war which was occurring in the country about which David says. Here it comes from Mahfouz's argument between his characters in the novel. The argument between kamal and his father Abdel Jawwad would suit better to highlight this situation. By young son kamal is being argued that it occurs at the time when the son tries to draw his father's attention towards his own respect to religious persons and men of Al Azhar to bring some grandeur to the teachers, because he too chooses this teaching profession to be for his career option. When he insists upon it the father explains to him.

"Don't mix things up. I revere Shaikh Al Mutawalli (a religious person) but I would far rather see you a respected civil servant than a man like him, even if you were to spread blessedness among the people, protecting them from the evil with emulates and charms.....every era has its men, but you refuse to understand" (Mahfouz & Hutchinson 1956,1991: 607, 50).

This statement marks a shift regarding religion and religious persons in the society. As an Islamic society where religion plays the main guiding role for its inhabitants and it shapes the discourse of people's lives. The argument claims to be in rejection mode, and it dives into another facet which is beyond its surface. The person who is being considered having a good respect to religion and religious people, who keeps seeking the blessings of Shaykhs and religious dignitaries, now believes that the time for all this is gone. Because the confessional statement declares in a blatant manner that this is not the need of the time and the time which persevered its relevance has gone now. The religion and religious figures have lost all their relevance. In fact the time itself has changed we moved into a new time zone which requires from us its own reverences and regards. We entered in another era and this time is quite different from that old one.

Third Volume: Al Sukkariyyah (1956) Sugar Street

Al Sukkariyya Sugar Street is the last volume of trilogy. This novel is set against the backdrop of Second World War and finishes with the rhetoric of change. The novel continuing with the patriarch's family whose third generation came into play, acquired the space fully. Through this changing space the author brings into light the shift which occurred in the society. The younger generation depicts all the socio- political nuances of the society in a more blatant way. They came forward do discuss the ideas and ideologies like communism and Islam frankly. In the novel women can be seen playing more role in the society too than the previous volumes. The freedom which was being discussed in the previous volumes now seems sprawling its wing freely. With the deteriorating health of both patriarch and matriarch, the scene can be termed in the prism of ending traditional way of life. Impact of War and its repercussions were discussed by the characters every now and then; certainly keep reminding the problematic political condition of the country. Furthermore, the novel brings the idea that the patriarchal society comes to an end, with each of his sons choosing their own way of life leaving those aspired by his father far behind.

Regarding this change Sara says in her review of the novel. "The architectural space of the store was no longer his; this space that was central to his activities, 'the meeting place for his friends and lovers, and the source of his renown and prestige' is no more. It is the end of an era" Zakzouk, (August, 2021).

The idea of change and ending an era, about which Sara talks, comes through the transformation which was taking place in the society. Indeed it was the modernity which ushered in pushing the tradition back. The author himself describes the process of modernization, even though the renovation works undertaken at that juncture in the city. As one of the protagonists shares a news about a coffee house, where he used to sit along with his friends was about to change into a modern cafe. The memories of the coffee house and evenings there, along with his friends makes one of his characters nostalgic, when he listens the news of it getting destroyed. It compels the author to criticize the act in a blatant manner. He abruptly compares the Abduh's coffee house to Pyramid of Egypt. He fears perhaps one day will come, if the human being will come to know the stones of the famous Pyramids can be used for any purpose, they will not hesitate to dig the stones out from there.

He notes

Kamal did not answer but remarked sadly, "have you heard? It (the coffee house) will soon be demolished so a new structure can be built on its ruins. This historic spot will vanish forever." his friend replies good riddance! Let these catacombs disappear so a new civilization can rise above them." At this Kamal says "you are right. I advocate demolition of the pyramids if some future is discovered for the stones" (Mahfouz, & Hutchinson, 1956,1991: 837,43).

At another point the ending an era is marked by the author when he describes the women in the street. Because for the old ones it was a matter of surprise when they see them roaming freely in the market and streets. They consider it as that time has gone now when the women used to sit in the houses like Amina used to do. With Amina's disappearance from the scene those days also finished. As, one of the protagonist and a friend of Abdul Jawwad Muhammad Iffat makes an observation. "It's the fashion now. Girls crowd into the streets, and men don't trust them anymore. Have not you heard Shaykh Hasanayn sing, what startling things we see: the gentlemen and the lady both at the barbershop'?" (Mahfouz, & Hutchinson, 1956,1991: 831,39).

Allen Roger takes us towards one another aspect of the society: the corruption, extremism and the chaos in the country. Indeed, it was the situation of the country both in thirties and forties of the last century.

He says

Indeed, the chaos and corruption in government, the atmosphere of terrorism and violence, and the drastic extremism of both left and right are captured most effectively in the novels of Najib Mahfiiz (b. 1911) written during this decade, culminating in the justly famous Trilogy (*Al-Thulkth?yah-Bayna al-Qasrayn*, *Qasr al-Shawq*, and *al-Sukkariyah*.) (Allen, 1981: 25-39)

This scene perfectly captured by the author when two grandchildren of the patriarch Seyyid Ahmad Abd al Jawwad, two brothers Abd al Mun'im and Ahmad, one becomes atheist and the other a Muslim brotherhood activist. At the end both of them were arrested by the authority and put into jail on the charges of extremism and sedition. Abd al Mun'im was arrested because he was a Muslim brother hood activist and he used to organize meetings with his fellow activists at his home. And Ahmad was an editor in a new man magazine. He used to write articles based on communist and socialists' ideology. The conversation between Kamal (uncle of Abd al Mun'im and Ahamd) and his friend Riyaz Qaldas sheds light on that prevailing situation well enough.

Riyaz asks Kamal

Is there any new development concerning them?" "They have gone with many others to the prison camp at al Tur in Sinai." Riyaz inquired jovially, "The one who worship God and the one who does not." "You must worship the government first and foremost if you wish your life to be free of problems" (Mahfouz, & Hutchinson, 1956,1991: 968-969, 305,306).

The quoted text from the book sheds light on the nature of cruelty perpetuated by the state on the people. The authoritarianism does not allow the citizens to propagate any other idea other than state sponsored one. Both the Islamists and atheists are being looked through the same prism. Even the ideas perpetuated by them show their non-satisfaction towards state and its sponsored idea.

One very interesting theme of Mahfouz seems to be religion and science he advocates for scientific development and nocks the door of science every now and then. Here one of the characters of the novel meets his cherished editor of a magazine which the young man follows routinely. They have a chat and the editors seem to advising the young man about

the need of the time, and the value of science which is going to lead the world leaving every other knowledge system behind, even the religion. After a formal introduction to the editor (Mr Adli Karim), he starts preaching Ahmad.

We must study the sciences and absorb the scientific mentality. A person who does not know the science he is not a citizen of twentieth century, even if he is a genius. Artists too must learn their share of science. It's no longer just for the scientists. Yes, the responsibility for comprehensive and profound knowledge of the field as well as for research and discoveries in it belongs to the scientists, but every cultured person illuminate himself with its light, embrace its principles and procedures and use its style. Science must take the place that prophecy and religion had in the ancient world." The editor continues by saying after a pause: study literature as much as you want, but pay more attention to your own intellectual development than to the selection you are asked to memorize. And don't forget modern science. In addition to Shakespeare and Schopenhauer, your library must contain Comte, Darwin, Freud, Marx, and Engels. Be as zealous about this as if you were religious. And remember that each age has its prophets. The prophets of this era are the scientists" (Mahfouz, & Hutchinson, 1956,1991: 853,81).

The idea behind this paragraph is that this is the time for science now without that no development can be foreseen. This is the era where development of the society can be based on science only. The technology can be gained by scientific knowledge; the knowledge system must be based on scientific manner. Science has acquired the status of prophets who can run and mould the society according to its own choice. The age of religion and prophet hood is gone now. The modern era prophets are Comte, Hegel, Marx, Engels, and Darwin. So what the society needs now is to change their religion if they wish to progress and develop. We must remember Amina the wife of Al Seyyid Ahmad Abd al Jawwad and even Al seyyid Ahmad. They were the religious people. Amina still roves around the shrines and mosques to seek God's blessings to cure his husband's ailment, and Abd al Jawwad with all his faults keeps calling God every time, and he keeps seeking God's refuge every now and then. Even Khadija and Ibrahim Shuakat Ahmad's parent are worried about Ahmad and his way of thinking. For them the idea of science and its prevalence are a kind of deviation from the real path.

Therefore, the author is very much realistic to note the social change and the forces which were standing on the doorstep to challenge the old order of the society. It was not only the modern day arms and artilleries which were introduced in Egypt, but new concepts and modern knowledge system were also experimented. Therefore, the author stresses upon the fact that if you want an inclusive development, you must follow the science as your religious duty. Every one of us must learn the modern tools of the development: no one should be left behind even those who studies literature must go for the modern one. At the same time the author criticizes the old version of knowledge and literary trends in general and Islamic seminaries in particular for the social backwardness. Where he says “From the Mosque University of Al Azhar and from the Dar al Ulum teachers college have come a sickening type of literature that has left the generations of Egyptians with rigid minds and broken spirits” (Mahfouz, & Hutchinson, 1956,1991: 853,81).

Conclusion

The unique context of Egypt and its encounter with the west and its impact on the society as a whole was explored in the paper. An attempt was made to unearth undercurrents of the society through the novels Cairo Trilogy (1957), These novels have documented the socio-political upheavals of Egyptian society which occurred in the first half of the twentieth century, particularly during the period of both the World Wars. It was the time when the country witnessed not only political chaos which brought two revolutions within a span of three decades but also the clash of ideas and the onslaught of modernity stirred the sensibilities of intellectuals. The debate over Islam and modernity became a root cause to choose between science and religion. As a result of this challenge posed by modernity a set of other ideologies infiltrated into the society like communism and socialism. The society, being based on Islam and its traditional values responded by attempting to revive Islam and its ethics. Apart from this, political upheavals and economic constraints created a lot of fuss both in the public and private spheres.

In this backdrop the selected novels written by Mahfouz, unearthed those undercurrents of the society in a perfect manner. The famous *al Thulathiyyat* (the trilogy) by portraying a patriarchal family of Cairo brings not only the tradition and modernity to face each other but also the subjects like science and religion, ethics and morality and

epistemology all being discussed by the various characters of Mahfouz.

References:

- Al Arabi (2006) *Naguib Mahfouz*, Ministry of Information State of Kuwait.
- Allen, Roger (1981) Contemporary Egyptian Literature *Middle East Journal*, Vol. 35, No. 1, pp. 25-39 (15 pages) <https://www.jstor.org/stable/4326146>
- Badavi, M M (1993) *A short History of Arabic Literature*, Clarendon Press, London.
- Castronovo, D. (1991) Review *Commonweal* <http://www.complete-review.com/reviews/mahfouz/cairo2.htm>
- El Enani, Rasheed (1993) *Naguib Mahfouz, the pursuit of meaning*, Routledge, London.
- El Shabrawy, Charlotte, (Summer 1992) Naguib Mahfouz, the art of fiction No.29, *The Paris Review Foundation*, Iss. 132 <https://www.theparisreview.org/interviews/2062/the-art-of-fiction-no-129-naguib-mahfouz>
- Hafez, S. (1976), The Egyptian Novel in Sixties *Journal of Arabic Literature*, Vol. 7 p.68-84 URL: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/4182965>
- Issa & Mahfouz, Naguib & Hutchins, William & Kenny, Lorne & Kenny, Olive. (1991). *Palace of Desire*. World Literature Today. 65. 759. 10.2307/40147802.
- Khaduri, M. (1970) *Political trends in the Arab World, the Role of ideas and ideals in politics*, The Johns Hopkins Press London.
- Mahfouz, Naguib (1991) *Al Sukkariyyah, al Mu'allafaat al Kamilah, al Mujallad al Thani* Maktabah Lebanon, (1991) Translated by Hutchinson, W. M. Samaan A. B. (1992) American University Press, Cairo.
- Mahfouz, Naguib (1991) *Bain al Qasrain, al Mu'allafaat al Kamilah, al Mujallad al Thani* Maktabah Lebanon, Translated by William Maynard Hutchinson and Olive E Kenny, *Palace Walk* (1990) American University Press, Cairo.
- Mahfouz, Naguib (1991) *Qasr ul Shawq, al Mu'allafaat al Kamilah, al Mujallad al Thani* Maktabah Lebanon, Translated by William Maynard Hutchinson and Olive E Kenny, *Palace of Desire* (2011) New York: Anchor Books .
- Marsot, Afaf Lutfi Al Sayyid (1985) *A short history of modern Egypt*, Cambridge: Cambridge university Press.

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Mehrez, S. (2003) *Egypt's cultural war; politics and practices*, Routledge 270 Madison Ave, New York.

Pasha, A. K. (1994) *Egypt's Quest for Peace, Detriments and Implication*. National Publishing House 23 Darya Ganj New Delhi India.

Pipes, Daniel. (February 12 1990) Washington Times
<http://www.danielpipes.org/872/palace-walk>

Richard Dyer, (7/2/1991) Reviews *Boston Globe* <http://www.complete-review.com/reviews/mahfouz/cairo2.htm>

Said, E. W. (2000) New York Review of Books, November 30,
<http://www.kirjasto.sci.fi/mahfouz.htm>

Salmavi, M. (2001) *Naguib Mahfouz at Sidi Gaber: reflections of a Noble laureate*, American university Press, Cairo.

Wood, M. (1998) The Use of the Pharaonic Past in Modern Egyptian Nationalism” *Journal of the American Research Center in Egypt, Vol. 35* p.179-196 Published by: American Research Center in Egypt Stable URL: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/40000469>

Zakzouk, Sara. (August, 2021) A portrait of Egypt in Flux: in Naguib Mahfouz’s Palace Walk, *Cultural Trip*,
<http://theculturetrip.com/africa/egypt/articles/a-portrait-of-egypt-in-flux-naguib-mahfouz-s-palace-walk/>

<http://www.elaph.com/ElaphWeb/ElaphLiterature/2005/8/84131.htm>

<http://www.naguib-mahfouz.com/life.htm>

<http://egyptartsacademy.kenanaonline.com/my/topics/58294/posts/10601>

[http://forum.selze.net/showthread.php/10397-%D9%86%D8%AC%D9%8A%D8%A8-%D9%85%D8%AD%D9%81%D9%88%D8%B8-\(%D8%AC%D9%88%D8%A7%D8%A6%D8%B2\)](http://forum.selze.net/showthread.php/10397-%D9%86%D8%AC%D9%8A%D8%A8-%D9%85%D8%AD%D9%81%D9%88%D8%B8-(%D8%AC%D9%88%D8%A7%D8%A6%D8%B2))

http://www.coptichistory.org/new_page_1136.htm

<http://theculturetrip.com/africa/egypt/articles/a-portrait-of-egypt-in-flux-naguib-mahfouz-s-palace-walk/>